

Application of Islamic Religious Values on Construction Workers (Case Study: Pt. Alcos Graha Jaya)

Nurlaelah¹, Basit Al Hanif², Otti Ilham Khair³

^{1,2}Civil Engineering Department, Faculty of Engineering, UMJ, Jl. Cempaka Putih Tengah XXVII, Jakarta 10510

³Government Science College Abdi Negara, Jl. Raya Lenteng Agung No.37 A, Jakarta 12630

ABSTRACTS: Workers in a construction company are a very important element for the whole company. Therefore, the presence of workers who have high enthusiasm and outstanding achievements in their fields is very important, so that they can create optimal performance. Workers who are able to provide good performance will have a positive impact and produce high-quality work. To achieve this goal, there are several factors that support, one of which is applying religious values, especially in the Islamic context to construction work. By using the questionnaire method given to construction workers at PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA, regression results were obtained with a t value of 11.290 greater than t table 2.00958, while the correlation result is 0.850 which means that there is a perfect correlation between the application of Islamic values and the performance of construction workers in the contractor company.

KEY WORDS: Islamic Values, Construction Worker Performance

INTRODUCTION

Construction projects have 3 (three) main constraints in their implementation, namely Cost, Quality and Time. Ideally a construction job, carried out at a low cost, good quality and fast time, so that the project owner is satisfied with the resulting project. To fulfill it, construction workers are needed who can properly manage all the materials needed, heavy equipment used, administrative systems, health and safety of construction work, and others. If construction workers cannot carry out their work properly, it will cause construction failure or construction delays and have an impact on increasing the cost of work (cost overrun).

As research by Arkinci, et al (2006) in Wiyana (2012), which states that failures in construction can occur after the construction process is complete or even during the maintenance period. If the detection of construction failures is done late, this will result in increased costs for repairs of about 6 to 12% of the total construction cost, and about 5% for maintenance costs. About 20-40% of construction failures occur during the execution stage, with 54% caused by labor skill deficiencies and the remaining 12% caused by poor quality materials.

Failure in construction work refers to a situation where the work does not meet the specifications agreed in the contract, either partially or completely, as a result of fault on the part of the service user or service provider. These failures are the result of a variety of factors. According to Oyfer (2002), "construction defects" in the US are caused by human factors

(54%), design (17%), maintenance (15%), materials (12%), and unexpected factors (2%).

Oyfer's research above is in line with the research of Worcup et al (2016) in Nurlaelah (2023) which states that the construction industry accounts for 57% of non-value added activities (NVA) carried out by construction workers. These NVA activities are activities that can cause construction failures and or delays, such as overproduction, inventory, defects, motion, transportation, processing, waiting.

With the research data related to construction failures and delays caused by human factors, especially the performance of construction workers above, a solution is needed that can improve the situation. One of them is by applying religious values, especially Islamic religion to construction workers. This is also to anticipate the tight competition that exists making contractor companies must be able to maximize the potential and capabilities that exist, especially in human resource management.

Islamic values are part of what shapes human culture and habits in general, including in the construction company environment. These values become the basis for behavior in the organization or at work, which is carried out with the intention of worship and the hope of Allah's pleasure alone. The application of Islamic values in work can increase employee morale and achieve company goals and progress optimally.

According to Hidayat, et al (2006) Islam encourages its people to work hard, based on moral values such as akhlaq or ethics. This ethics becomes an important equipment that

allows various professions to achieve their goals safely and also as sincere worship to Allah. Abraham (2001) suggests that as Muslims, there are some personal values that should be emphasized as we work, which are based on the good behavioral examples of Allah's messengers. These values aim to improve human interactions within the environment. One very important value is piety. In this context, Prophet Muhammad (PBUH) asserted that "it is the pious people with good behavior who are most worthy of entering heaven." Trust can also be seen as the key to faith in Allah. In an Islamic perspective, work is an inseparable part, starting from the intention of work that not only seeks material gain in the world, but also rewards in the hereafter. This intention will affect the individual's effort at work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Islamic Perspective On Work

By Nuraini (2022), in an Islamic perspective, work is considered as an inseparable unity, starting from the intention to work which not only aims to seek material benefits in the world, but also to get rewards in the hereafter. When our intention in working is as an act of worship, it includes two goals, namely fulfilling physical and spiritual needs, both materially and non-materially. Therefore, since the purpose of work is not only limited to seeking material wealth, the efforts made not only involve physical strength, but also involve non-physical strength, such as prayer.

Thus, the result of work is not only dependent on physical effort alone, but also related to the attitude of tawakal. This means that when a person has tried his best but the results are not in line with his expectations, he will still accept the results of the work with gratitude. He will not constantly feel disappointed, because he realizes that man's obligation is only limited to trying, while it is Allah who determines the final result. Islamic spiritual values provide motivation to always work, try and be grateful for the results. The results of work appraisal will be addressed by a Muslim with a positive work attitude (feeling satisfied). Allah's words in the Qur'an: "Work, and Allah will see your work, and His Messenger and the believers, and you will be returned to Allah, Who knows the unseen and the manifest, and He will give you what you have done" (Q.S. At-Taubah: 105).

Shafique et al. (2015) noted that work ethics in Islam is a crucial aspect for companies and individual employees, and staff can benefit through the implementation of Islamic work codes. Islam also emphasizes the importance of following ethical values in all aspects of life to achieve success. The spiritual values in Islam provide encouragement to continue working, striving and being grateful for the results. As a result, a Muslim will respond to his/her work appraisal results with a positive work attitude, i.e. a feeling of satisfaction.

B. Construction Worker Performance

In the opinion of Mangkunegara (2010), Human Resource performance is a term derived from the word Job

Performance or Actual Performance (work performance or actual achievement achieved by a person). Therefore, it is concluded that HR performance is work performance or work results (output) both quality and quantity achieved by HR unity over a period of time in carrying out its work duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to it. In Melyana et al (2022), mentioned that Anil et al. (2019) cited by Kesavan et al. (2021) indicated that the lack of labor productivity is one of the main challenges in the construction industry, especially in developing countries. When labor productivity is low, the project is at risk of being late and resulting in significant additional costs, and vice versa. One of the factors that affect labor productivity is capability.

Meanwhile Soeharto (2001) in Wijayanti et al (2021), Labor is an asset in project management that is essential for completing tasks in a project as a whole. Field labor in construction projects is divided into two categories, namely supervisors or foremen and workers or laborers. This labor group consists of several roles, including fitters, helpers, and foremen. Labor performance reflects the work results obtained in completing assigned tasks, and it is determined by factors such as time, dedication, experience, and skills.

Furthermore, factors that influence labor performance on the quality of work in building construction include motivation, skills, discipline, education, experience, wages, age, environment, and proficiency. (Soeharto, 2001), (Ervianto, 2003) (Moh. Nurul Huda, 2014) noted this.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted at the contractor company PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA, following the research stages as in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 Research Stages

According to the figure above, the stages of this research include:

1. Literature study, aimed at finding definitions of Islamic Religious Values and Construction Worker Performance, as well as to formulate a research questionnaire.
2. Making a research questionnaire based on the results of the literature review.
3. Distributing research questionnaires to research respondents, namely construction workers at PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA.
4. Analyze the results of the questionnaire with SPSS statistics using the Regression and Correlation formulas.

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Meanwhile, to make it easier to understand the research, a research framework is made as shown in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. Research framework

Based on the framework above, the hypothesis formulation is:

Ho: Islamic Religious Values have no positive effect on the performance of construction workers.

Ha: Islamic Religious Values have a positive effect on the performance of construction workers.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of 51 construction workers at PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA were willing to help fill out the questionnaires needed

in this study. Furthermore, quantitative analysis was carried out using regression and correlation analysis with the help of SPSS to answer the hypotheses that had been formulated. The results are:

a. Regression Analysis

The results of data processing using SPSS, obtained the following regression analysis results

Variables Entered/Removed ^a			
Model	Variables Entered	Variables Removed	Method
1	Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam ^b		Enter

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pekerja Konstruksi
b. All requested variables entered.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.850 ^a	.722	.717	2.241

a. Predictors: (Constant), Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	640.340	1	640.340	127.459	.000 ^b
	Residual	246.170	49	5.024		
	Total	886.510	50			

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pekerja Konstruksi
b. Predictors: (Constant), Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	6.105	3.380		1.806	.077
	Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam	.850	.075	.850	11.290	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kinerja Pekerja Konstruksi

Figure 3. SPSS statistical analysis results for regression

From Figure 3 above, it can be determined that the regression equation is $Y = 6.105 + 0.850X$, a positive value means that the higher the application of Islamic values, the better the performance of construction workers at PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA.

Furthermore, hypothesis testing is carried out in 3 ways, namely:

1. Significance value of 0.000 is smaller than 0.05, then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

2. Comparing t count with t table, the results show that t count is 11.290 greater than t table 2.00958 with degrees of freedom (df)=n-2=51-2=49 and $\alpha=0.05/2=0.025$.
3. Regression Curve

Figure 4. Regression Curve

In the curve above, it can be seen that the t count is in the right (positive) area.

According to the results of the 3 ways of Hypothesis Test above, all of them conclude that the application of Islamic values has a positive effect on the performance of construction workers at PT.ALCOS GRAHA JAYA.

b. Correlations Analysis

		Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam	Kinerja Pekerja Konstruksi
Nilai-Nilai Agama Islam	Pearson Correlation	1	.850**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	51	51
Kinerja Pekerja Konstruksi	Pearson Correlation	.850**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	51	51

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Figure 5. SPSS statistical analysis results for regression

Based on the correlation table above, the 2 tailed significance value is 0.000, smaller than 0.05, which means it is significantly correlated. While the value of r count (pearson correlation) is 0.850 greater than r table (0.361) which means it is perfectly correlated between the application of Islamic values and the performance of construction workers at PT.ALCOS GRAHA JAYA.

The results of the regression and correlation analysis above are in line with the research of Hadisi (2014) and Wahab (2012), which prove that belief in religion has a significant impact on understanding religious values, which then affects individual performance. Because based on the opinion of Musrin (2004), Islamic values are essentially a collection of life principles, teachings on how humans should live their lives in this world, which one principle with another is interrelated to form a whole unit that cannot be separated. Value is also an idea or concept about what a person thinks and considers important in his life. Through values, we can

determine whether an object, person, idea, or way of behaving is good or bad.

Value is also something inherent in a person that is expressed and used consistently and stably. Values are also considered as benchmarks and principles for weighing or judging something about good or bad, useful or useless, appreciated or reproached. The form of Islamic values must be transformed in the field of human life. Islamic religious values have a huge influence on social life, even without these values humans will descend to a very low level of animal life because religion contains curative elements against social diseases. Islamic values are the characteristics of Islamic teachings that are beneficial to humanity. These values not only manage the relationship between humans and God but also the relationship between humans and nature.

However, it must be noted that this research was only carried out on one contractor, PT ALCOS GRAHA JAYA. Perhaps if carried out on other contractors, the results will differ from the regression and correlation values. It could be that in other contractors there is no relationship at all between the application of Islamic values and the performance of construction workers. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct further research in several other contractors, so that comprehensive conclusions can be drawn regarding this research.

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